

Study of the genus *Anthrenus*, subgenus *Florilinus* from the Eastern Palaearctic Region. Part 1: species from Mongolia (Coleoptera: Dermestidae: Megatominae)

J. Háva

Private Entomological Laboratory & Collection

Rýznerova 37/37, CZ-252 62 Únětice u Prahy, Prague-west, Czech Republic

e-mail: jh.dermestidae@volny.cz

ORCID 0000-0001-8076-9538

Key words: Taxonomy, new species, Coleoptera, Dermestidae, *Anthrenus*, Mongolia, Palaearctic Region.

Abstract. *Anthrenus (Florilinus) baganuur* **sp. nov.** from Mongolia is described, illustrated and compared with a similar species. The new species differs by the structure of antennae and male genitalia.

Introduction

The subgenus *Florilinus* Mulsant et Rey, 1868 of the genus *Anthrenus* Geoffroy, 1762 recently contains 41 species Worldwide (Háva 2023a-e, 2024). Only two species are known from Mongolia (Mroczkowski 1965, Zhantiev 1973, Háva 2006, 2024).

The subgenus is characterized by antennae consisting of 8 antennomeres. Males differ from females by the shape of the antennal club. In males, the terminal antennomere is longer than the penultimate one; in females it is as long as the penultimate one. Adults can be found on plants, but also in households, where the larvae are harmful to different commodities of natural origin. They are feared pests in museum collections (Peacock 1993, Háva 2023a-e).

Material and methods

The size of the beetles or of their body parts can be useful in species recognition and thus, the following measurements were made:

total length (TL) - linear distance from anterior margin of pronotum to apex of elytra.

J. Háva

elytral width (EW) - maximum linear transverse distance.

The material mentioned is deposited in following collection: (JH), Jiří Háva, Private Entomological Laboratory & Collection, Únětice u Prahy, Prague-West, Czech Republic.

Specimen of the species described here are provided with red printed labels with texts as follows: „HOLOTYPE *Anthrenus (Florilinus) baganuur* sp. nov. Jiří Háva det. 2025”.

Result

Anthrenus (Florilinus) baganuur sp. nov.

Figs. 1-3

Description. Female. Body measurements (mm): TL 2.3 EW 1.4; body brown, small, oval (Fig. 1). Dorsal surfaces covered by intermixed brown and white scales. Head covered by white scales, posteriorly with brown scales. Palpomeres and labrum brown. Antennae consisting of 8 antennomeres, antennomeres brown, terminal antennomere longly oval (Fig. 2). Antennal fossa long and broad, finely punctured. Frons with median ocellus. Eyes with entire median margin. Pronotum covered with white and brown scales, brown scales forming spot discally. Scutellum small, triangular. Elytra with brown and white scales, white scales forming fasciae (Fig. 1). Epipleuron short, narrow, with white scales. Individual scales small and triangular. Ventral surface covered with white scales, abdominal ventrites covered by white scales only. Ventrites I-V without spots in the middle, covered by white scales. Prosternum with white scales only. Metasternum with white scales only, without any large patch at lateral margins. Legs brown with white scales and white setae. Aedeagus (Fig. 3).

Female. Unknown.

Differential diagnosis. The new species similar to the two *Florilinus* species known from Mongolia, but differs from them by the structure of antennae and male genitalia (visually according to broad body form very similar to *A. kaszabi* but differs from it by the structure of antennae and male genitalia).

Material. Holotype, male, “Mongolia, 5 km W Bagan-Nur [= Baga Nuur], 31.7.-1.8.1975” - JH.

Etymology. Toponymic, named according to Baga Nuur lake in the Zavkhan Aimag (Mongolia).

Figs. 1-3. *Anthrenus (Florilinus) baganuur* sp. nov.: 1- habitus, dorsal aspect; 2- antenna; 3a, 3b - male genitalia.

Figs. 4-11. *Anthrenus (F.) kaszabi* Zhantiev, 1973: 4 - antenna of male; 5- antenna of female; 6- dorsal scales; 7 - aedeagus; *Anthrenus (F.) mongolicus* Zhantiev, 1973: 8 - antenna of male; 9 - antenna of female; 10 - dorsal scales; 11 - aedeagus (according to Zhantiev (1973)).

J. Háva

Remarks. Mroczkowski (1965) mentioned the species *A. museorum* (Linnaeus, 1767) from Gobi Aimak, but the specimen belong to *A. kaszabi* Zhantiev, 1973.

Acknowledgements. I am very indebted to Larry G. Bezark (California, USA) for the comments and English revision to the manuscript.

REFERENCES

- Háva J. 2006: Contribution to the knowledge of Dermestidae (Coleoptera) from Mongolia. - *Acta Musei Reginaehradecensis* S. A. 31: 83-87.
- Háva J. 2023a: Study of the genus *Anthrenus*, subgenus *Florilinus* from the Oriental Region. Part 1. *Anthrenus* (*Florilinus*) *declamator* sp. nov. from Taiwan (Coleoptera: Dermestidae: Megatominae). - *Munis Entomology & Zoology*. 18 (1): 57-59.
- Háva J. 2023b: Study of the genus *Anthrenus*, subgenus *Florilinus* from the Oriental Region. Part 2. *Anthrenus* (*Florilinus*) *laosensis* sp. nov. from Laos (Coleoptera: Dermestidae: Megatominae). - *Natura Somogyiensis*. 40: 5-8.
- Háva J. 2023c: Study of the genus *Anthrenus* subgenus *Florilinus* from the Oriental Region. Part 3. A new species from Indonesia, Sumba Island (Coleoptera: Dermestidae: Megatominae). - *Munis Entomology & Zooogy*. 18 (2): 746-766.
- Háva J. 2023d: Study of the genus *Anthrenus* subgenus *Florilinus* from the Oriental Region. Part 4. A new species from Malaysia (Coleoptera: Dermestidae: Megatominae). - *Munis Entomology and Zoology*. 18 (supplement): 1820-1822.
- Háva J. 2023e: Study of the genus *Anthrenus* subgenus *Florilinus* from the Afrotropical Region (Coleoptera: Dermestidae: Megatominae). - *Faunitaxys*. 11 (46): 1-3.
- Háva J. 2024. *Dermestidae World* (Coleoptera). - World Wide Web electronic publication (open in 2004): <http://www.dermestidae.wz.cz> (version 2018, update September 2024).
- Mroczkowski M. 1965: Ergebnisse der Zoologischen Forschungen von Dr. Z. Kaszab in der Mongolei. 11. Silphidae partim, Dermestidae (Coleoptera). - *Folia Entomologica Hungarica*. 17: 183-185.
- Peacock E. R. 1993. Adults and larvae of hide, larder and carped beetles and their relatives (Coleoptera: Dermestidae) and of derodontid beetles (Coleoptera: Derodontidae). *Handbooks for the Identification of British Insects*. 5: 1-144.
- Zhantiev R. D. 1973: Ergebnisse der Zoologischen Forschungen von Dr. Z. Kaszab in der Mongolei. Nr. 321. Dermestidae (Coleoptera). *Annales - Historico-Naturales Musei Nationalis Hungarici*. 65: 187-194.

Received: 11.12.2024

Accepted: 18.03.2025